

FORMS OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON THE ACMEOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE PROCESS OF INFORMATIZATION OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In the article digitization which has made jaraè more extensive today, the competencies poured into the activities of the subjects of Education jaraène are theoretically analyzed. Thus, the article provides information about the content of acmeology and the importance of applying the acmeological approach to the educational process, the features of preparing future educators for professional activity through self-development based on the acmeological approach.*

Keywords: *educational subjects, distance education, media, mediacompetence, digitization, innovation management, acmeology, acmeological approach, self-development, self-control, self-education.*

Among the urgent tasks is the development of interactive technologies for informatization of educational premises in higher educational institutions, special attention is paid to improving the pedagogical mechanisms for creating an integrated educational environment. The creation of an electronic information educational environment of an educational institution is not a purely technical issue, but for this the use of scientific and modern information telecommunications technologies of the institution in the educational system is carried out in the following areas:

- information and telecommunication technologies as an object of study, that is, students will receive general concepts and skills in new information technologies, their components and areas of use;

- information and telecommunication technologies as a means of teaching, that is, on the basis of modern information and pedagogical technologies, students are given knowledge, and lectures, practical and laboratory classes are organized on the basis of modern computer software;

-creation of an informatization, analysis and forecasting system as a means of managing the educational jaraène, that is, to increase the efficiency of all work activities of the educational institution, including educational, spiritual and educational and research work;

-creation and implementation of modern information systems as a means of carrying out scientific and pedagogical research of students and professors, that is, to increase the effectiveness of research and pedagogical research among teaching professors and students in an educational institution.

A pedagogue working with information technology tools must meet the following competency requirements:

- The fact that it embodies the qualities of mediacompetence;

Currently, it is difficult to imagine the establishment of an educational jaraèn without taking advantage of the possibilities of computer technology. The convenience of the interface, which is part of computer software tools, provides an opportunity for educators to effectively master modern information technologies. Thus, the capabilities of information and communication

technologies can be effectively used in the development of personality-oriented education, in the formation of students' creative abilities.[3]

Modern information technology allows solving new didactic issues in micro and macrodunè, such as the phenomenon in complex devices, biological systems and the teaching of jaraèns based on the use of computer graphics and modeling, the presentation of physical, astronomical, kimèvie, biological jaraèns that occur at a very large speed at a convenient time.

Therefore, one of the promising directions for the introduction of modern information technologies in education is computer modeling of phenomena and jaraèns. Computer models will be in tune with the content of a traditional lesson and will give a great impression to the teacher on the computer screen, on the display of many effects, on the organization of new, unconventional educational activities of students.

Currently, much attention is paid to modernization and development in our society, both from a socio-economic point of view and to the specifics of the individual. Therefore, there is a need to research the mechanisms of mental phenomena and self-development of the individual.

The decline in production in the country, changes in the professional structure of society mean the relevance of studying the relationship between the characteristics of professional activity and the process of self-development of a person. This in turn makes it possible to acmeologically correct professional training in the education system.

Acmeology is a science that studies the characteristics of human and personality development, as well as looking for ways to reach the highest point in this process, resorting to the achievements of other areas in pedagogical terms.

For the first time, the term " acmeology " was used in 1928 by the Russian psychologist Nikolai Rybnikov. Thus, analogous to pedology, an interdisciplinary area of pedagogy that studies the development of the child, he proposed to call the science of the development of mature people. In the middle of the 20th century, another Soviet psychologist Boris Ananiev of acmeology, determined his place in the system of Human Sciences.

In the process of informatization of education, on the basis of an acmeological approach, it is possible to achieve an improvement in professional training of future educators through self-development.

The acmeological approach is an important factor in the formation of the ability to creativity in future educators. Personal abilities and ways to make them content. The system of formation of the ability to creativity.

Subjects of the educational system and the educational process in the implementation of various types of creative activity. This approach involves the identification of positive qualities of the subjective qualities of the educator as a positive feature of the personality and professional path, which makes it possible to achieve high results in the profession. These qualities include:

- openness to learning a new experience;
- to develop an alternative project of professional parts aspiration;
- adequate self-regulation of one's own professional behavior ability;

The defining characteristics of professional maturity are the ability to innovate and the presence of pedagogical skills, professional qualifications and strong motivation to improve pedagogical skills and solve educational problems. To achieve professional maturity, it is necessary to be professionally formed.

The concept of " professional formation " is used as the achievement of production efficiency by the subject of Labor on the basis of the level of ownership of the profession and the formation and manifestation of professionally important characteristics, knowledge, skills, experience and skills in specific labor activities. The fact that a subject of Labor has a high level of professional qualifications in a specific field of activity is referred to as skill.

A.K.Markova noted that the following types of professional formation highlighting the stages of:

- "the improvement of the individual himself as an expert;
- * internal professional supervision;
- * perceived qualities of a specialist, size;
- * full image of the person himself as a specialist;
- the ability to self-develop with the help of a profession and compensate for missing features.

It is worth saying that in the system of preparing future educators for professional activity, the following forms of self-development can be manifested:

- * understanding of the system of spiritual and moral values associated with the profession;
- * knowledge acquisition and analysis of personal experience;
- * acceptance of specific professional qualities of experienced educators and the desire to work on oneself for the like;
- * maximum mobilization of personal strength and resources to achieve the goal set forward;
- * the emergence of a sense of satisfaction in labor;
- * striving for self-personal development;
- the individual must have self-control in his behavior.

Thus, each future educator in the possession of scientific knowledge and skills will also expand the reserve of knowledge, and at the same time, he will also carry out the process of self-development.

It is for this reason that the educational process of educators is self-education, in the process of which both the study of the world by students and the processes of self-study are carried out at the same time.

The self-education of future educators, independent work on oneself, plays an important role in self-development. When a student, of his own free will, goes in search of scientific information in the enrichment of his knowledge, he develops and improves himself, in addition to receiving education in real meaning. And in the implementation of this process, the independence of future educators is manifested in the following.

In conclusion, it can be said that at the stage of self-development assessment at the stage of self-development assessment, future educators evaluate by giving a negative or positive self-assessment in one relationship or another.

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